

THE MECHANISM OF THE ACTION OF CHARCOAL ON POTASSIUM NITRATE. PART II. STUDY OF THE REACTIONS

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A detailed study of the action of charcoal on KNO_3 and of the influence of temperature on the interaction has been undertaken. Evidences from all the experiments show that charcoal acts in two different stages (i) $4\text{KNO}_3 + 2\text{C} \rightarrow 4\text{KNO}_2 + 2\text{CO}_2$ and (ii) $4\text{KNO}_3 + 3\text{C} \rightarrow 2\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 + \text{CO}_2 + 2\text{N}_2$. These are followed under suitable conditions by the flash reaction: (iii) $\text{KNO}_2 + \text{KNO}_3 + 2\text{C} \rightarrow \text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 + \text{CO}_2 + \text{N}_2$.

Reaction (iii) is the major reaction in the interaction and proceeds through the dissociation of the potassium nitrite, produced in (i) into potassium oxide, nitric oxide and nitrogen tetroxide. This is followed by a chain of vigorous reactions between the nitric oxide and nitrogen tetroxide with charcoal, and the fixation of the carbon dioxide, thus produced, in the K_2O as potassium carbonate. The proportion of $\text{N}_2 : \text{CO}_2$ in the reaction is 2 : 1.

Depending on conditions, the reaction may proceed smoothly to completion, the reactions (i) and (ii) going on concurrently producing carbon dioxide and nitrogen in the ratio of 3 : 2, or it may develop speed, become violent and produce a flash. In the flash stage, the reaction (iii) occurs, potassium nitrite being then produced from the nitrate in two ways: (a) by reduction with charcoal as in (i) and (b) by direct rupture into potassium nitrite and oxygen. The reaction chain, initiated by potassium nitrite, proceeds in full swing and charcoal burns in the mixture of nitric oxide and oxygen producing a flash. The proportion of $\text{N}_2 : \text{CO}_2$ in the flash reaction is as 1 : 1.

In Part I (Oza and Shah, *J. Univ. Bom.*, 1942, 11, iii, 56) it has been shown that the usual reaction $4\text{KNO}_3 + 5\text{C} \rightarrow 2\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 + 3\text{CO}_2 + 2\text{N}_2$, attributed to the action of charcoal on potassium nitrate is, in all probability, made up of at least two consecutive reactions proceeding as

and that the reaction (ii) is, probably, the net result of several side or consecutive reactions. It has also been shown there that the interaction with 20% charcoal at 390° steadily develops speed and the reaction (i) becomes violent and then culminates into a flash if KOH is included in the system, the reaction (ii) then slackens without the production of flash if both the carbon dioxide and nitrogen are pumped off continuously as they are formed.

With a view to elucidating the factors controlling the flash the effect of (a) mass of charcoal and (b) temperature, on the interaction is studied in detail and to substantiating the evidence obtained, the interaction between charcoal and (i) potassium nitrite and (ii) mixtures of potassium nitrite and potassium nitrate of known composition is also investigated. The results of these investigations are set out in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

The materials used, the apparatus and the mode of work were exactly the same as those described in Part I (*loc. cit.*).

The Effect of Mass of Charcoal

The occurrence of flash in the interaction between potassium nitrate and 20% charcoal when KOH is included in the system and its absence when the evolved gas is all pumped off led to examination of the effect of more than 20% charcoal under the two conditions.

Experiments with 25 and 30% charcoal showed that flash occurred in all the experiments under both the conditions. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Flash expts. at 390° with 0.45 g. KNO₃ and 25 and 30% charcoal with and without KOH in the system

(a) without KOH

C.	T in min.	Gas evolved (composition in c.c.).				Gas evolved (% composition).				Ratio.				Residue (g.)		
		Total.	N ₂ .	CO ₂ .	NO.	CO.	N ₂ O ₂ .	N ₂ .	CO ₂ .	NO.	CO.	N ₂ O ₂ .	N ₂ :CO ₂ .	K ₂ CO ₃ .	KNO ₃ .	KNO ₂ .
25%	4	96.7	37.6	52.8	0.4	5.9	—	38.9	54.6	0.4	6.1	—	1:1.4	0.237	0.0235	0.0323
30	4	108.1	40.8	60.9	3.1	3.7	—	37.7	56.3	2.9	3.0	—	1:1.5	0.258	0.0133	Trifle

(b) with KOH

25	3	95.7	36.9	52.5	2.0	4.3	1.0	38.5	54.9	2.1	4.5	1.1	1:1.4	0.218	0.0200	0.0344
30	3	101.4	37.3	56.3	4.5	3.3	0.7	36.5	55.5	4.4	3.3	0.7	1:1.5	0.248	0.0124	0.0300

TABLE II

Expts. at 390° with 0.5 g. KNO₃ and 14, 16, 18, 20 and 22% charcoal to examine the interaction in stages

C.	T (min.)	Gas evolved (composition) in c.c.				Diff. bet. consecutive stages.	Ratio N ₂ :CO ₂ from 15.	Gas evolved (% composition).				Residue (g.)						
		Total.	N ₂ .	CO ₂ .	NO.			CO.	N ₂ .	CO ₂ .	NO.	CO.	K ₂ CO ₃ .	K ₂ CO ₃ per cent of N ₂ .	KNO ₃ in g.	KNO ₃ (diff. between stages).	KNO ₂ in g.	
14	8	22.8	7.9	13.8	0.1	0.5	7.9	13.8	1:1.7	35.4	61.9	0.4	2.3	0.055	0.007	0.0034	—	0.4218
..	18	42.8	16.0	26.3	0.1	0.4	8.1	12.5	1:1.5	37.4	61.4	0.2	1.0	0.110	0.0068	0.0031	0.0000	0.3531
..	36	64.6	24.1	39.8	0.2	0.5	8.1	13.5	1:1.7	37.3	61.6	0.3	0.8	0.171	0.0075	0.0066	0.0034	0.2800
..	75	90.8	34.4	55.3	0.7	0.4	10.3	15.5	1:1.5	37.9	60.9	0.8	0.6	0.228	0.0056	0.0091	0.0025	0.1815
16	—	32.4	12.1	19.9	0.1	0.3	12.1	19.9	1:1.6	37.3	61.4	0.3	1.0	0.089	0.0074	0.0044	—	0.3814
..	—	55.6	21.0	34.1	0.2	0.3	8.9	14.2	1:1.6	38.0	61.4	0.3	0.6	0.142	0.0060	0.0143	0.01	0.2963
..	80	79.1	26.5	52.1	0.8	0.7	5.5	17.0	1:3.1	33.5	64.6	1.0	0.9	0.1605	0.0034	0.0195	0.0052	0.2390
..	135	100.9	33.9	66.1	0.9	1.0	7.4	15.0	1:2.0	33.6	65.5	0.9	1.0	0.2054	0.0061	0.0270	0.0075	0.1632
18	5	14.2	3.0	10.3	0.5	0.4	3.0	10.3	1:3.4	26.1	70.0	3.5	2.9	0.0160	0.0053	0.0009	—	0.4618
..	18	31.0	8.1	22.8	0.5	0.4	5.1	11.5	1:2.1	..	70.0	1.5	2.0	0.0346	0.0036	0.0012	0.0003	0.4176
..	45	56.3	17.6	38.3	0.4	1.0	9.5	16.5	1:1.7	30.7	66.8	0.7	1.8	0.0970	0.0065	0.0016	0.0004	0.3345
..	62	83.6	26.8	54.8	1.7	1.3	9.2	16.5	1:1.8	31.7	64.8	2.1	1.6	0.1648	0.0074	0.0037	0.0021	0.2500
..	93	108.6	37.9	69.2	1.0	1.4	10.2	14.4	1:1.4	34.2	63.7	0.9	1.3	0.2270	0.0061	0.0056	0.0019	..
20	4	19.3	2.2	15.8	0.7	0.6	2.2	15.8	1:7.2	11.4	81.9	3.7	3.1	0.0136	0.0062	0.0009	—	0.4571
..	14	36.0	7.0	27.3	0.9	0.8	4.8	11.5	1:2.4	26.4	69.3	2.5	2.2	0.0435	0.0062	0.0009	0.0000	0.4172
..	27	61.8	18.5	41.8	0.8	0.7	11.4	14.5	1:1.3	30.0	67.8	1.3	1.1	0.1068	0.0055	0.0022	0.0013	0.3186
..	70	108.5	36.3	69.5	1.1	1.6	17.8	27.7	1:1.6	33.4	64.5	1.0	1.5	0.2130	0.0060	0.0035	0.0013	0.1608
22	2.5	24.3	5.3	17.7	0.8	0.5	5.3	17.7	1:3.3	21.8	72.8	3.3	2.0	0.0176	0.0033	0.0146	—	0.4256
..	5.0	64.3	19.1	43.4	0.8	0.5	13.8	25.7	1:1.9	30.0	67.4	1.2	1.6	0.1008	0.0060	0.0188	0.0042	0.2985
..	7.0	112.4	42.1	64.1	1.4	4.6	23.0	20.7	1:0.9	37.5	57.1	1.2	4.1	0.2713	0.0074	0.0430	0.0042	0.0542

Flash

The interaction is considerably accelerated by increase in the proportion of charcoal, time required for the production of flash (3 to 4 min.) being much less than that in the experiments with 20% charcoal (about 24 min.). The proportions of the components of both the solid residue and the evolved gas in the two sets of experiments compare favourably with those in the flash experiments with 20% charcoal and with each other.

It is evident that the cause for the occurrence of flash is to be sought for in the composition of the reacting mass more than in any superimposed condition such as inclusion of KOH in the system.

Evidently if the interaction be examined at several intermediate stages between the beginning and end of the reaction with varying proportions of charcoal, the nature and amounts of the reaction products at intermediate stages may be revealed and thus it may throw light on the mechanism of the reactions responsible for the production of flash. Series of experiments were therefore performed with 0.5 g. of potassium nitrate and 14, 16, 18, 20, and 22% charcoal and in each series reactions were allowed to proceed to different extents and the products of the interaction examined as usual. As the flash occurred with 22% charcoal, experiments with higher proportion of charcoal were not deemed essential. The results of this series are given in Table II and graphs of the volumes of nitrogen against amounts of potassium carbonate shown in Fig. 1.

The results show that :

(i) The ratio $N_2 : CO_2$ (column 6) is fairly constant, averaging to 1 : 1.6 in all stages with 14% C and fluctuated very much with others. This ratio steadily increases in the initial stage with the amount of charcoal, being as much as 1 : 7.2 with 20% charcoal (the corresponding stage with 22% C is very vigorous). In the flash stage this ratio becomes 1 : 0.9.

(ii) The amounts of potassium nitrite (column 10), which show irregularity when end stages are compared in accordance with the previous observations (Part I, Tables I and II), show more or less complete uniformity from stage to stage in any single set of experiments. Its amount is the greatest in the end stage with 16% C, and an amount comparable with it is found only in the flash stage with 22% C. This implies that the charcoal content of the reacting system has much to do with the production of potassium nitrite and also that perhaps a certain optimum concentration of this substance is demanded by the flash reaction and that this probably operates through time factor (column 2). Column 11 shows that there are fluctuations in the amounts of potassium nitrite from stage to stage up to 18% C but after this its amount, at all stages, in any single set, becomes steady. Thus with 20% and 22% C, there is a constant difference in the amount of potassium nitrite from stage to stage indicating a constant rate of its formation and decomposition. This rate is far higher in reactions with 22% C than with 20% C.

(iii) The amounts of potassium carbonate formed (column 9) increase proportionately with the production of nitrogen in all experiments thus showing that the mass of charcoal influences the production of nitrogen and potassium carbonate in practically the same way. With 22% C the production of potassium carbonate is greater in the flash stage than in the preceding stages; a similar quantity is formed with 18% C as well. Here, however, the vigour of the reaction, modulated by the charcoal content of the system, is very slow. This would mean that for the same quantity of potassium carbonate there is less nitrogen formed during the flash stage than in the preceding stages.

(iv) Nitric oxide and carbon monoxide (column 7) are produced in small amounts. Their amounts are irregular and appear, in general, to depend on the proportion of

charcoal used. The amounts of nitric oxide and nitrogen tetroxide are usually higher in the initial stage and in the flash-stage than in other stages. The amounts of the oxides of nitrogen found in any stage should depend upon (a) pressure under which the experiment is conducted,

low pressure raging for a long time tending to draw some of the gases formed and normally undergoing further reaction with charcoal, out of the place of their origin in spite of their great reactivity to charcoal; (b) quantity of charcoal then present in the system, an insufficient quantity permitting their escape; and (c) the rate with which they are formed at the place of their origin, since charcoal, even if present in sufficient

amount, may not be able to abruptly reduce a large quantity of the gases suddenly formed. It is likely that the cause (a) operates in the initial stages, (b) operates in the few isolated stages (e.g. in experiments with 18% C, where unusual quantity of potassium carbonate is found to have been formed in absence of flash and (c) operates in the flash.

(v) Potassium nitrate is present in the residue even after the flash though in small amount.

It was observed that the mercury of the pump was practically unaffected, except at the start in experiments with 14% C and the effect was greater, the greater the percentage of charcoal used and was noticeable in 18% and 21% C.

Effect of Temperature

One of the most important indications of the above series of experiments is that the ratio $N_2 : CO_2$ tends to become unity in the flash stage. With a view to testing this observation a series of experiments was planned to separate the gaseous reaction products of the flash stage from those of the preceding stages. The experiments were conducted with 0.3 g. of potassium nitrate and 20% charcoal. Smaller quantities were used to avoid repeated fractures of the apparatus by the violence of the reaction. The temperatures used were 395°, 400°, 410° and 420°. Higher temperatures were preferred in order to observe at the same time the effect of temperature. The evolved gas was continuously pumped off till the flash occurred, when the time was noted and the tap P (Fig. 1, p. 57, Part I) was turned off and the gas on the pump side collected along with that already pumped off (A). The tap was next opened and the gaseous products of the flash stage collected separately (B). The gases (A) and (B) and the residue were analysed. The results are given in Table III. These show the same general features as before and further that the ratio $N_2 : CO_2$ is, on an average, 1 : 1.7 in (A) and 1 : 1.2 in (B). In view of the facts that (a) the rapidity of the reaction near the flash stage does not permit, complete separation of the gas (A) from the gas (B) and (b) that some potassium nitrite

is present in the residue, it would appear reasonable to suppose that in the flash reaction the ratio $N_2 : CO_2$ tends to become 1 : 1.

An attempt was made to examine the reaction at 405° in stages. The results are set out in Table IIIA and compare favourably with the results of a similar experiment with 22% charcoal at 390° (Table II). It will be seen in the table that the ratio $N_2 : CO_2$, referred to differences in their amounts between consecutive stages, is more than 1 : 2.1 in the stages preceding the flash and about 1 : 0.9 in the stage attending the flash.

TABLE III

Flash expts. at higher temps. to separate the gaseous products formed before the flash (A) from those formed during the flash (B).

Temp.	Time for flash to pass.	Gas evolved (composition in c.c.).						Ratio.				Gas evolved (% composition)			Residue (g.)		
		Total.	N_2 .	CO_2 .	NO.	CO.	$N_2 : CO_2$.	N_2 .	CO_2 .	NO.	CO.	K_2CO_3 .	KNO_2 .	KNO_3 .			
395°	24 min.	75.8	29.1	43.8	1.5	1.4	1 : 1.5	38.4	57.7	1.9	1.6	0.1945	0.0158	0.0143			
400	13.0	72.6	28.2	41.9	1.5	1.0	..	38.8	57.7	2.0	1.3	0.1820	0.0183	0.0169			
410	4.5	75.0	29.3	43.3	1.5	0.9	..	38.9	57.7	2.1	1.2	0.1870	0.0143	0.0145			
420	3.0	76.9	30.3	44.9	1.3	0.4	..	39.4	58.3	1.7	0.5	0.1905	0.0214	0.0109			

(A) Gas evolved before flash.

(B) Gas evolved during flash.

Total gas (c.c.)	Composition.				Ratio.				Total gas (c.c.)	Composition.				Ratio.				Total gas (c.c.)	Composition.			
	N_2 .	CO_2 .	NO.	CO.	$N_2 : CO_2$.	N_2 .	CO_2 .	NO.		CO.	N_2 .	CO_2 .	NO.	CO.	$N_2 : CO_2$.	N_2 .	CO_2 .		NO.	CO.		
41.1	15.3	25.2	0.4	0.3	1 : 1.65	37.2	61.3	1.0	0.7	34.6	13.9	18.5	1.1	1.1	1 : 1.33	40.2	53.5	3.2	3.2			
39.3	14.7	24.2	0.2	0.3	..	37.1	61.6	0.5	0.7	32.9	13.7	17.2	1.3	0.7	1 : 1.25	41.7	52.3	3.9	2.1			
43.5	16.1	27.0	0.2	0.2	1 : 1.7	36.9	62.4	0.5	0.5	31.3	13.4	15.7	1.3	0.7	1 : 1.17	42.8	50.1	4.1	2.3			
44.2	15.9	27.9	0.2	0.0	1 : 1.75	36.1	63.2	0.5	0.0	32.5	14.4	16.5	1.0	0.4	1 : 1.15	44.3	50.8	3.1	1.2			

TABLE IIIA

Flash expt. at 405° to examine the interaction in stages with 20% charcoal

$KNO_3 = 0.4$ g.

Stage No.	Gas evolved (composition in c.c.).						Ratio.		Gas evolved (%).				Residue (g.).		
	Total.	N_2 .	CO_2 .	NO.	CO.	N_2O_3 .	$N_2 : CO_2$.	N_2 .	CO_2 .	NO.	CO.	N_2O_3 .	K_2CO_3 .	KNO_2 .	KNO_3 .
1	36.8	11.3	24.0	0.1	0.5	0.9	1 : 2.1	30.7	65.2	0.3	1.4	2.5	0.0707	0.0180	0.2700
2	48.2	14.8	31.8	0.0	0.6	1.0	1 : 2.1	30.7	65.9	0.0	1.3	2.0	0.1025	0.0185	0.2367
3 Flash	94.6	37.6	52.5	2.5	1.3	0.8	1 : 1.4	39.8	55.5	2.6	1.5	0.8	0.2367	0.0267	0.0223

The observations in Table II have also shown that there is a rapid rate of formation and consumption of potassium nitrite under conditions conducive to the production of flash; and that potassium nitrate is present in the residue after the flash. From these it would appear that both potassium nitrate and potassium nitrite may take part in the reaction producing the flash. This together with the facts that the ratio $N_2 : CO_2$ approximates to 1 : 1.5 in all experiments wherein the reaction proceeds to end, becomes 1 : 1.7.2 in the initial stage with 20% charcoal

and tends to be 1:1 in the flash stage of the reaction, confirm the observation recorded in Part I regarding the composite nature of the reaction: $4\text{KNO}_3 + 5\text{C} \rightarrow 2\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 + 3\text{CO}_2 + 2\text{N}_2$, and indicates that in the flash reaction equivalent quantities of the nitrite and the nitrate may be reacting with charcoal to produce carbon dioxide and nitrogen in the ratio 1:1.

The Action of Charcoal on (i) Potassium Nitrite and (ii) Mixtures of Potassium Nitrite and Potassium Nitrate

Since oxides of nitrogen are present in all experiments it would seem that a study of (i) the thermal decomposition of potassium nitrate and (ii) the action of charcoal on (a) potassium nitrite and (b) known mixtures of potassium nitrite and potassium nitrate may provide important information on the course of the reactions under investigation. The thermal decomposition of potassium nitrite (Oza and Shah, *J. Univ. Bom.*, 1942, 11, iii, 70) was studied in this connection. The results showed that potassium nitrite dissociates at its melting point (about 419°) into potassium oxide, nitric oxide and nitrogen tetroxide according to the equation:

and the nitrogen tetroxide formed acts upon the undecomposed potassium nitrite to produce nitrogen or nitric oxide as: $2\text{KNO}_2 + \text{N}_2\text{O}_4 \rightarrow 2\text{KNO}_3 + \text{N}_2$ (2) and $\text{KNO}_2 + \text{NO}_2 \rightarrow \text{KNO}_3 + \text{NO}$ (3). The potassium nitrate formed in (2) and (3) undergoes scission into potassium nitrite and oxygen under the experimental conditions, the process being aided by the nitric oxide present in the system which removes oxygen from the system as nitrogen tetroxide, the latter influencing the reactions (1), (2) and (3).

An investigation on the effect of charcoal on potassium nitrite showed that the reaction starts in the vicinity of 390°, the exact temperature depending slightly on the proportion of charcoal used. The reaction is always violent* becoming so within a few seconds of its start and then comes to a stop, the violence being accompanied by scintillation of charcoal particles but no flash. The violence of the reaction is very great and the apparatus often cracked even with only 0.2 g. of potassium nitrite.

An examination of the gaseous products and the solid residue showed the presence of (i) nitrogen†, carbon dioxide, nitric oxide, nitrogen tetroxide and carbon monoxide, and (ii) potassium carbonate, potassium nitrite and potassium nitrate. Potassium oxide, azide, cyanate and hyponitrite were tested for and found to be absent. The apparatus and the method of experimentation were the same as before. After evacuating the apparatus the column was surrounded by the electric furnace maintained at 350° and the temperature gradually raised. Not the slightest evolution of any gas was observed till the temperature at which the reaction became violent was reached. Near this temperature a few bubbles of gas were soon followed by a sudden release of a large volume of gas. The temperature was noted. The results of these experiments are given in Table IV and the potassium carbonates formed plotted against the evolved nitrogen in Fig. 2.

The results show that (i) total quantity of the evolved gas increases with the increase in the percentage of charcoal; (ii) there is a steady change in the composition of the evolved gas as the proportion of charcoal used increases: the ratio $\text{N}_2:\text{CO}_2$ passes steadily from 1:0.4 with 5% charcoal to 1:0.8 with 100%,‡ the average value of the ratio being 1:0.5; (iii) potas-

* The vigour of the reaction could be slackened only by very cautious regulation of temperature if the proportion of charcoal is reduced to 5%.

† A small quantity of nitrous oxide was detected in the slow reaction experiment with 5% charcoal.

‡ Percentage of charcoal refers always to the mass of nitrate or nitrite or mixture of the nitrate and nitrite used.

sium nitrite is always present in the residue and also potassium nitrate. The amount of potassium nitrite consumed in an experiment is proportional to that used in the experiment, while the amounts of potassium nitrate formed are small being appreciable only in the slow experiment with 5% charcoal; (ii) the linear relationship between the quantities of potassium carbonate and nitrogen formed is evident from the figure.

TABLE IV
Decomposition of KNO_3 in presence of different amounts of charcoal

C%.	KNO_3 taken g	Temp. of reaction.	Gas evolved in c.c. at N.T.P.				Gas evolved in %.				Residue (g.).			Ratio $N_2:CO_2$	
			Total	N_2	C_2	NO.	CO.	N_2	CO_2	NO.	CO.	K_2CO_3	KNO_3		KNO_2
5*	0.1149	412-13*	8.9	5.9†	2.3	0.6	0.1	66.1	25.9	7.0	1.0	0.0423	0.0264	0.0344	1:0.7
10	0.1405	406-07	19.2	12.5	5.1	1.4	0.2	65.0	26.6	7.2	1.2	0.0774	0.0011	0.0498	"
15	0.1255	403-04	20.1	12.9	5.4	1.5	0.3	64.3	27.0	7.5	1.2	0.0874	0.0022	0.0214	"
20	0.1242	401-02	22.9	14.5	6.3	1.8	0.3	63.4	27.6	7.7	1.3	0.0901	0.0019	0.0142	"
25	0.1884	398-9	33.0	20.3	9.3	2.6	0.8	61.5	28.2	7.9	2.4	0.1249	0.0024	0.0330	1:0.45
50	0.1216	391-2	25.1	13.8	7.8	2.2	1.3	55.2	31.7	8.6	4.5	0.0943	—	0.0139	1:0.56
100‡	0.1153	385-6	26.2	12.5	9.6	2.6	1.8	47.6	36.6	10.0	6.8	0.0820	—	0.0135	1:0.77

It is both interesting and important to notice that it is the average value of the ratio $N_2:CO_2$ which is 1.0:0.5, and not the actual value, in any single experiment. The latter depends

FIG. 2

on the proportion of charcoal used. This indicates that the reaction is complex. In view of the fact that nitric oxide and nitrogen tetroxide are invariably present in the gaseous reaction products it would seem likely that these form the intermediate products in the reaction culminating in the formation of potassium carbonate, carbon dioxide and nitrogen. Such a view is consistent with what is known about the thermal decomposition of potassium nitrite (*loc. cit.*) and about the behaviour of nitric oxide (Shah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2661) and of nitrogen tetroxide (Trivedi, Bombay University M.Sc. thesis, 1941) to charcoal.

The results of the action of charcoal on known mixtures of potassium nitrate and potassium nitrite are given in Table V.

The results show that (i) in all experiments the interaction becomes violent; the violence is accompanied with flash up to 25% potassium nitrite and of scintillation but no flash in experiments with 100%. No flash was actually noticed in the 50% experiment;

(iii) the time needed for the violent reaction to occur is less, the greater the quantity of potassium

* In this experiment alone the reaction could be controlled. Heating continued cautiously for 15 min.

† Some nitrous oxide was detected in the nitrogen here.

‡ KOH was included in the apparatus in this experiment; the N_2O_3 formed there was 0.33 c.c.

nitrite used and whenever a flash is produced there is always a definite time lag before it is observed; (iv) with the increase in the percentage of potassium nitrite there is an increase in the production of potassium carbonate and nitrogen and a decrease in the production of carbon dioxide; (v) both potassium nitrite and potassium nitrate are present in the residue and some nitric oxide, nitrogen tetroxide and carbon monoxide are always present in the gaseous products.

TABLE V

Expts. at 405° with known mixtures of KNO₂ and KNO₃ with 2% charcoal.
Wt. of the mixture = 0.2 g.

KNO ₂	KNO ₃	Reaction violent within:	Composition of gas evolved in c.c. (N.T.P.)				Gas evolved (%)				Residue (g.)			
			Total.	N ₂	CO ₂	NO	CO	N ₂	CO ₂	NO	CO	K ₂ CO ₃	KNO ₂	KNO ₃
0.0%	100.0%	7-8 min.	46.8	16.8	26.5	2.2	1.4	35.9	56.6	4.7	3.0	0.1186	0.0138	0.0021
6.25	93.75	6-7	45.4	17.4	26.3	1.6	1.2	37.2	56.6	3.4	2.6	0.1152	0.0106	0.0021
12.50	87.50	5-6	49.8	20.0	27.5	1.5	0.8	40.2	55.2	3.0	1.6	0.1211	0.0106	0.0118
25.00	75.00	4-5	44.1	18.5	23.4	1.4	0.7	41.9	53.5	3.2	1.6	0.1263	0.0106	0.0177
50.0	50.0	0-1	40.2	20.3	18.0	1.4	0.6	50.5	44.8	3.5	1.6	0.1250	0.0117	0.0024
100.0	0.0	Immediate	32.1	23.4	8.8	2.5	0.4	63.4	27.5	7.7	1.4	0.1277	0.0414	0.003

KOH solution included in the apparatus in the last expt. gave 0.55 c.c. of N₂O₃.

DISCUSSION

The observations recorded in Parts I and II throw light on the mechanism of the action of charcoal on potassium nitrate. Potassium nitrate (m.p. 335°), decomposing into nitrite and oxygen only on strong heating, becomes reduced to the nitrite in presence of charcoal at 250°. The fact that the mass of charcoal accelerates the interaction whereas the mass of potassium nitrate has no similar effect shows that the surface of charcoal plays an important part in the interaction. Further, the fact that no oxygen or carbon dioxide is evolved at 250° and the residue still shows the presence of nitrite indicates that oxygen of the nitrate is retained by charcoal in some state (Rhead and Wheeler, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 103, 461; Keyes and Marshall, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 158; Shah, *loc. cit.*) on its surface. Again the production of carbon dioxide in the greatest quantity in the commencing stage shows that the retained oxygen is given off at a suitable temperature as,

The facts that the quantities of potassium nitrite present in the residue are never great and nitrogen and potassium carbonate are always produced along with carbon dioxide show that the action of charcoal on potassium nitrite, leading to the formation of nitrogen and potassium carbonate, constitutes the second concomitant stage in the interaction. The observation that in some stages in the interaction the amount of nitrogen formed is greater even than that of carbon dioxide, taken together with the fact that the average value of the ratio N₂:CO₂ in the interaction between potassium nitrite and charcoal is 1:0.5 makes it highly probable that the second stage of the interaction is

The absence of potassium oxide and the production of potassium carbonate and nitrogen in linear proportions with respect to each other suggest that the reaction (ii) is a simple one. But the facts that in the interaction between potassium nitrite and charcoal (a) the actual composition of the products depends on the relative proportions of the reactants, (b) the interaction, once started becomes almost necessarily violent giving out scintillations of charcoal particles, (c) nitric oxide and nitrogen tetroxide are always present in the gaseous reaction products and (d) some potassium nitrate is always present in the residue show beyond doubt, that the reaction is dependent on the reactions involved in the thermal decomposition of potassium nitrite:

with the difference that, in the present case, the extent of the reactions (iv) and (v) is very limited as the nitrogen tetroxide and nitric oxide (Shah, *loc. cit.*) react readily and completely with charcoal, * as

so that the balanced reaction (iii) proceeds from left to right. The removal of potassium oxide as

accelerates it. Thus, the presence of charcoal induces a chain of vigorous reactions by its action on nitric oxide and nitrogen tetroxide. The reaction (ii) may therefore be represented, severally and compositely as

The presence of carbon monoxide in the gases is due to the tendency of the sorbed oxygen in charcoal to come off in this form as the charcoal particles scintillate during their rapid interaction with oxides of nitrogen.

The interaction between potassium nitrite and charcoal constitutes a major stage in the reaction under study. It is this stage which decides whether the reaction shall be smooth or violent. At a low temperature and with a low percentage of charcoal the reaction is slow. With rise in temperature and increase in the percentage of charcoal it gains speed and above the optimum temperature and percentage of charcoal, it becomes violent and produces a flash. Both the interactions: $\text{KNO}_2 + \text{C}$ and $\text{KNO}_3 + \text{C}$, become violent at about the same temperature and in both the reactions the products are almost exactly similar. The important difference between the two violent reactions is that while the latter becomes so only after a definite time lag and is accompanied with a flash, the former is violent with start and is never accompanied with flash but only scintillation of charcoal particles. Before the flash is produced the $\text{KNO}_2 + \text{C}$ reaction gains great speed in which potassium nitrite is produced and used up at a constant high rate. In view of the facts that (i) potassium nitrate is always present at the beginning and the end of the flash reaction and (ii) the violent reaction between potassium nitrite and charcoal is

* These reactions, supposed to proceed through sorbed oxygen, are represented in this way only for the sake of convenience.

never accompanied with flash it appears likely that both potassium nitrite and potassium nitrate take part in the production of flash. This and the fact that the proportion of $N_2:CO_2$ in the flash stage tends to become 1 : 1, make it highly probable that the reaction in the flash stage may be

Direct experimentation with 50% of the nitrite and the nitrate shows that the reaction is instantaneous, as expected, produces nitrogen and carbon dioxide in the ratio of 1 : 1, also as expected, and is, in general, similar to the flash reaction but *does not produce any flash*. The flash is seen in all experiments up to 25% potassium nitrite in all of which violence sets in less than a minute. The cause of the flash lies, evidently, in something circumstantial. The only conceivable difference between the two reactions, which we may call the natural and the artificial, may be in the temperature condition of the reacting mass. Since the involved reactions are all exothermic, the local temperature of the reacting mass in the natural mixture may be higher than that in the artificial one and at the high temperature prevailing in the natural mixture, some of the potassium nitrate might undergo scission into potassium nitrite and oxygen; the nitrogen tetroxide from potassium nitrite might also produce oxygen under the equilibrium condition $2NO_2 \rightleftharpoons 2NO + O_2$, so that the flash stage in the interaction might correspond to the combustion of charcoal in oxygen and nitric oxide as

Thus, on the whole, the flash reaction may, severally and compositely, be thus represented:

The observations that the flash is accompanied with the production of larger amounts of nitric oxide, nitrogen tetroxide and carbon monoxide and that the production of flash is accelerated by increase in the proportion of charcoal and by a rise in temperature are in accord with this view.

* This might involve intermediate formation and oxidation of carbon monoxide as

